

Spectrochemical Parameters and Stereochemistry of some *p*-Mercaptoacetamidochlorobenzene (*p*-MCB) Complexes

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Crystal field splitting parameter, Δ ; Racah parameter, B and nephelauxetic co-efficient, β , have been calculated for *p*-MCB complexes of Cr(III), Ni(II) and Co(II). Stereochemistry of these complexes has been discussed on the basis of Δ value. Spectrochemical series, based on Δ , is found to be Cr(III) > Co(II) > Ni(II).

VERY recently Kakkar and Khadikar^{1,2} have determined the formation constants of some metal complexes of *p*-MCB. From the potentiometric study they have shown the formation of 1:2 complexes with Cr(III), Co(II) and Ni(II). We have now isolated these complexes and the present communication deals with the spectrophotometric study of the same. The crystal field splitting parameter Δ , Racah parameter B and nephelauxetic coefficient β have been calculated and stereochemistry and stability sequence have been discussed on the basis of these parameters.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R., B.D.H. or equivalent quality.

The ligand, *p*-MCB has been prepared by the method described by Poonia *et al.*³

The light absorbance measurements were made using Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra in solution of Cr(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes of *p*-MCB were recorded in the region 320-950 nm using acetone as solvent. The results are given in Table 1 (Figure 1).

Nickel (II)-*p*-MCB :

Octahedral Ni(II) complexes generally exhibit three absorption bands in the visible region around 330, 540, and 820 nm. These bands may be shifted to higher wave lengths with weaker ligand field.⁴ In the spectrum of nickel (II)-*p*-MCB three bands have been observed at 340, 660 and 725 nm. These observations suggest an octahedral structure for nickel (II)-*p*-MCB. The values of Δ , B and β for nickel (II)-*p*-MCB calculated following Ballhausen⁴ are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1.—SPECTROCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF SOME *p*-MCB COMPLEXES

Complex	λ_{max} nm	γ_{max} cm ⁻¹	ϵ_M	Δ , cm ⁻¹	B , cm ⁻¹	β
Cr(III)- <i>p</i> -MCB	410	24,390	24	17,544	716.09	0.779
	570	17,544				
	600	16,667				
Ni(II)- <i>p</i> -MCB	340	29,412	35	8,040	957.20	0.921
	660	15,150				
	725	13,790				
Co(II)- <i>p</i> -MCB	400	25,000	30	13,070	12,641.22	1.303
	500	20,000				

Cobalt (II)-*p*-MCB :

Octahedral cobalt (II)-complexes generally exhibit two absorption bands in the visible region around 460 and 550 nm. In the case of cobalt (II)-*p*-MCB two bands have been observed at 400 and 500 nm. This suggests an octahedral structure for cobalt (II)-*p*-MCB. Values of Δ , B and β , for this cobalt complex are also given in Table 1.

Chromium (III)-*p*-MCB .

The spectrum of Cr(III)-*p*-MCB showed two bands at 410 and 570 nm and a shoulder at 660 nm indicating octahedral environment⁶. The values of Δ , B and β are given in Table 1.

The octahedral stereochemistry finds further confirmation in the value of molar extinction coefficient (Table 1), since the octahedral complexes have ϵ_M of the order 10 and tetrahedral complexes have ϵ_M of the order of 10³.

Stability Order :

Based on the Δ values the stability sequence for Cr(III)-, Ni(II)- and Co(II)-*p*-MCB complexes is found to be :

Cr(III) > Co(II) > Ni(II), which do not agree with the Irving-Williams rule⁷. However, the order

Fig. 1.

— Cobalt(II)-*p*-MCB
 -x-x-x- Chromium(III)-*p*-MCB
 - - - - Nickel(II)-*p*-MCB.

is in agreement with the stability order given by Kakkar and Khadikar² based on the values of formation constants of these complexes. The greater stability of Co(II)-*p*-MCB complex compared with that of Ni(II) is probably due to partial oxidation of Co(II) to Co(III) as proposed by Kakkar *et al.*³ and/or due to additional stabilization by Jahn-Teller distortion⁹. As described by Khadikar and Gupta⁹ we observed 15% increase in Δ for Co(II)-*p*-MCB due to distortion.

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